

Prospects for Purun Woven Craftsmen (*Lepironia articulata* Retz) in Basarang Village, Central Kalimantan

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the total income of purun woven craftsmen, and determine the level of welfare of purun woven craftsmen in Basarang village, Central Kalimantan. Quantitative and qualitative research methods were carried out by census of 10 heads of families. The research results showed that the total income of purun woven craftsmen in one month varied because purun woven craftsmen also had other income from cutting rubber. Based on the productivity of research results in one month, it also varies, getting mat sheets ranging from 24 - 48 sheets with a selling price of Rp. 25,000,- per mat. The overall results when compared with the Regency or City Minimum Wage are still relatively low, because this income still does not meet the Regency or City Minimum Wage standards. If we look at the level of welfare of the purun woven craftsmen, it is still not enough to survive on a daily basis. The solution is to further improve the quality of the coloring process, utilize working time efficiently, try to create new motifs and establish coaching and training collaborations supported by village agencies. The hope is that purun craftsmen can make quality purun flattening tools that can meet adequate usage standards, pay attention to places where the coloring process has been given a roof, utilize working time more efficiently, so that productivity can increase and the results obtained will be greater while still creating quality. supported by new patterns and motifs that are able to compete.

Keywords: *Purun motif, productivity, income, purun craftsmen.*

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Introduction

Non-timber forest products (NTFPs) are a type of plant that grows widely both inside and outside forest areas. Even though the community has perceived the role of NTFPs as a source of income, the management system is still traditional so that the quality produced is still far from the expected standard and the price is still relatively low (Salaka, et al. 2012). NTFPs are a forest resource that has the advantage of being cooperative and having direct contact with communities around the forest (Hastanti, 2018). The NTFPs in question can come from plant roots, leaves, plant stems, fruit, sap, bark and can also come from wood stems. One of the natural resources which is non-timber forest products is NTFPs in the Basarang Village area, Basarang District, Kuala Kapuas Regency, Central Kalimantan Province in the form of the purun plant (*Lepironia Articulata* Retz Domin). Kuala Kapuas is a district in Central Kalimantan Province, Indonesia.

Optimizing the use of non-timber forest products as raw materials from purun, which is carried out by purun woven craftsmen with various creations through the creative economy, is a new concept that intensifies information and creativity by relying on ideas and knowledge from human resources as a

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production factor, which is starting to be recognized and has a very strategic role in economic development and business development.

The terms creative economy and creative industry are currently being developed in order to improve the economy, specifically Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). One of the developments in the creative economy in the research area is the development of handicrafts that make natural sources made from purun into woven crafts in the form of mats or bags and other products. Purun woven products are now increasingly creative in type and design, created by micro, small and medium businesses in the regions. With this existing potential, it is hoped that it will be able to improve the family economy, the community in Basarang village and the Family Welfare Empowerment (PKK) also encourages Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDES) to facilitate residents to develop their existing potential. Purun woven craftsmen process purun into finished goods with economic value. Purun craftsmen in this village can process it into finished goods in the form of mats or bags and various other forms of handicrafts. Purun is a type of grass plant that lives wild in swamp areas (Salaka, et al. 2012). Based on the background above, researchers are interested in finding out about the marketing prospects of purun in Basarang village, Basarang subdistrict, Kuala Kapuas district, Central Kalimantan.

Research Methods

This research was carried out in Basarang village, Basarang District, Kuala Kapuas Regency, Central Kalimantan, the research object was purun woven craftsmen using census respondents of 10 heads of families. This method uses descriptive data from interviews which are then analyzed. This analysis is carried out in descriptive form in which it tries to collect and compile data and then analyze it (Creswell, W.J., 2014). The analysis was carried out quantitatively, with calculation data using respective formulas such as income value (Boediono, 1992), fixed production costs (Sukirno, 2002), Total Income (Soekartawi, 2003), Productivity (Wijadja, 2022) and the level of welfare of the craftsmen purun weaving (Sukirno, 2002). Meleong (2000) added that all the data collected is the key to what has been researched. This condition occurs because one document can complement or support each other.

Results and Discussion

Processing

Purun plants have benefits in improving the community's economy. Asikin (2012): purun can be processed as raw material for making mats, hats, bags and other handicrafts. Hadi, S, et al (2024), stated that this type of weaving activity is the oldest work in the world. In the initial process of making purun mats, purun plants that are suitable for harvest are one year old with a length of more than 2 m, and if the purun plants are still young, the average size is usually still short, the stems are small and the manufacturing process will slow down. and also affects the selling value of the product. In Basarang village, farmers plant purun at the edge of the garden and the purun they plant must be given fertilizer. For standard fertilizer applications, farmers need 5 kg of urea fertilizer and 5 kg of lime mixed together and sprinkled around the plants. Fertilizer application is only done once a year because if fertilizer is not provided, growth will be slow and the quality of the purun will also not be good. Purun which grows wild and its growth is not monitored is rarely used as purun woven material (Sunardi and Istikowati, 2012).

The process of making mats begins with taking the purun raw materials by pulling them one by one which are deemed to be of good quality measuring more than 2 m, once deemed sufficient, the purun is washed with water to clean the stem of the purun, after that the top and bottom bases measuring more than 2 m are cut. must be the same, after that the purun is tied and dried in the hot sun for approximately 3 - 4 days or until completely dry, after drying the purun must be flattened so that the purun is flexible and easy to shape and makes the weaving process easier (Suprpto, 2019).

The method for flattening purun is by using wood and pounding it on a flat surface. After the flattening process to make it more attractive to buyers, the purun that has been flattened is colored red and green. For the coloring process, first light a fire in the stove using firewood, after that prepare a container or pan and add the water, wait until it boils, after boiling, add the color for one mat, usually half a tablespoon for one color, then add the purun that has been prepared then stir. -stir until smooth, the same goes for the next color, for a long coloring process until the color sticks to the purun and the same goes for the next color.

After the dyeing process is complete, the purun is removed to cool, then washed with water and dried in the sun for approximately one or two days depending on the weather, once it is considered dry the purun is ready to be woven. How to do the weaving by holding both feet to support the initial weaving so that the weaving does not move and so on. Patria (2015), states that there are two terms in weaving, namely arranging the warp and weft. The final process is finishing to perfect the craft, so that the craft made can look good and neat and the quality produced is also maximum. For the calculation of time when collecting data, it does not start by using a certain time standard for purun woven craftsmen, because the working time of craftsmen when starting to make a craft is not the same, some start working from 7 am and some start from 8 am, this is because there are other responsibilities. This is different from working hours in companies where working hours are set when starting work. So, there is a difference in the initial working time from one craftsman to another. This is what caused the initial recording of working time to only follow the working time of the purun weaving craftsmen. Yudistira (2021), stated that when compared with medium and large industries, the work productivity of small industries is still low. In Basarang village, purun woven craftsmen can make two types, namely plain, colorless mats and colored bakampat motif mats, which are a legacy from our ancestors that must be preserved.

Asikin and Thamrin (2012), stated that informal and traditional industries include the craft industry. This purun woven craft activity was formed on the basis of the habit of making woven crafts by craftsmen, and the tendency for women to become craftsmen is due to their desire and sense of responsibility to be able to help their husbands meet their daily needs. The types of crafts made by purun woven craftsmen for these 10 respondents were plain and patterned mats.

Purun woven craftsmen in Basarang village also have obstacles that often occur, such as weather factors and difficulty in getting purun raw materials, examples of other obstacles that often occur when applying color, such as firewood not being dry yet, causing uneven flames, Falling rain also hampers the drying process on the purun, because the purun woven craftsmen still use stoves so they don't have to spend money on gas. Some of the furnaces used for dyeing do not have roofs and some have roofs but can still get wet if it rains. Purun, which is shorter in size than the others, also slows down the weaving process and also makes it difficult to get purun raw materials. This work is done to increase family income. So, the level of productivity in making purun mat crafts is not really prioritized. Purun woven craftsmen in Basarang village generally prioritize their main job, some work as farmers and housewives, so their work does not only involve making purun woven crafts (Tata, et al (2016).

Suharto (2021), states that increasing productivity is due to the role of human resources, the speed of time used in making crafts depends on the craftsmen themselves. The faster the craftsman makes a woven purun craft, the more results he will get. And if the craftsman works with a good level of focus and doesn't do much outside of making a craft, then the time spent will be more effective. Because after all, productivity is expected to produce more and be accompanied by good quality (Anaroga, 2001).

Purun woven craftsmen in Basarang village obtain purun plants by buying one bunch of purun plants for Rp. 25,000,- one bundle can produce 4 mats with a mat size of 2 m long and 125 cm wide. Many purun plants grow where people live. This purun plant is easy to grow and does not require a certain season or time to grow because this plant is classified as a wild plant. Purun woven craftsmen take purun that are more than 2 m long and have a stem diameter of 2-8 mm, whereas to obtain such a size, care is needed by applying fertilizer (Tata, et al (2016).

Purun woven craftsman business requires initial capital to buy the main raw materials, the initial capital that must be spent, buying one bundle of purun costs IDR. 25,000,- and can produce 4 pieces of purun mat and buy 2 dyes for the price of 1 dye Rp. 50,000,-. To take purun raw materials, you don't need to spend capital and only spend capital to buy red dye at a price of Rp. 50,000,- per one ounce and green dye at a price of Rp. 50,000,- per one ounce, to finish these two colors, usually if you produce every day it takes approximately 1 month, if you rarely produce it, it will take longer to use up the dye (Tata, et al (2016).

Marketing Process

The results of field research show that the education levels of Purun craftsmen vary, some have graduated from elementary school and graduated from high school. It is known that the length of time worked has been passed down from generation to generation for up to 40 years, with varying age levels, this varying age level will result in the regeneration of purun woven craftsmen and make it easier to develop craft making in the future. The development of young people will be easier, because young people have a more innovative and more modern mindset. An innovative and modern mindset is an effort to increase creativity for the development and success of a business (Junaidah et al., 2018).

Working Time Productivity

Data from research regarding the work time productivity of purun woven craftsmen can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1. Recapitulation of Work Productivity of Purun Woven Craftsmen

NO	Name	Input/Kg	Output/day	Type	Size (m x cm)	Working Time/Hours
1	Rina	3	2	Mat	2 x 125	9
2	Sanah	3	2	Mat	2 x125	9
3	Galuh	3	2	Mat	2 x 125	9
4	Rahmah	1.5	1	Mat	2 x 125	4
5	Santi	1.5	1	Mat	2 x 125	4
6	Lisnawati	1.5	1	Mat	2 x 125	5
7	Nurmiah	1.5	1	Mat	2 x 125	4
8	Hikmah	3	2	Mat	2 x 125	9
9	Sumiah	3	2	Mat	2 x125	9
10	Amamah	3	2	Mat	2 x125	9

Source: Research Data (2022)

The recapitulation of the working time and productivity of purun woven craftsmen in one day is different for each respondent, the difference in productivity and working time of respondents is due to other jobs as a side job such as cutting rubber. The hope of the craftsmen is that they can produce on a larger scale and also produce handicraft products that will produce better quality, and the profits they will get will also be greater. If currently the production process is still manual, in the future with more modern tools it is hoped that it can accelerate the development of the production of woven purun crafts, to increase the selling value of a product and produce a craft that is neater, stronger, more attractive and of better quality. The results will be better, but it does not eliminate the traditional value elements of the craft itself, because the traditional value of a craft is what will give the uniqueness and characteristics of the purun woven craft product. According to Isni, et al (2022), working time productivity refers to how effectively and efficiently a person or group of people uses their working time to achieve the desired results. Increasing the productivity of working time means maximizing the output or results of each unit of time invested in the work.

Hastuti (2003), states that if a person gets older there will definitely be a decrease in productivity. Age will have a big influence on worker productivity if the work carried out is classified as heavy work and is adjusted to a predetermined amount of working time and limited rest time. So, if done continuously for

a long time it will definitely cause a decrease in productivity. A decrease in productivity occurs because a worker is considered old, making it difficult to work with stable energy for a long time. In contrast to workers who are young and have strong energy. The conclusion is that the job of making purun weaving is not limited to age alone but depends on a person's skill and tenacity to be able to produce more production. Craftsmen who are still relatively young and have strong physique and energy, if they do not have motivation, enthusiasm, patience, experience and skills, their productivity will not be optimal. In contrast to craftsmen who already have experience, even though they are old and physically declining, the enthusiasm, skills and experience they already have will make a craftsman remain productive, because weaving work is not a hard job.

The research results show that an important factor that causes differences in the productivity value of each craftsman is the level of discipline or level of focus of the craftsman when making a craft. Hasibuan (2003), states that there needs to be motivation in order to work more effectively. As well as the awareness to continue to make further improvements (Sinungan, 2003), meaning, the mental attitude of the craftsmen is what makes the craftsmen aware that by working focused they will be able to increase productivity and can be of great benefit to them.

Total Working Time

The results of calculating the working time productivity of purun woven craftsmen in Basarang Village, Basarang District, Kuala Kapuas Regency, Central Kalimantan Province are presented in the following table.

Table 2. Total Working Time

No	Respondent's Name	One Month Working Hours
1	Rina	216
2	Sanah	216
3	Galuh	216
4	Rahmah	96
5	Santi	96
6	Lisnawati	120
7	Nurmiah	96
8	Hikmah	216
9	Sumiah	216
10	Amamiah	216

Source: Research Data (2022)

The results of calculating the productivity of working hours of purun woven craftsmen in one month vary, based on respondents Rina 216 hours, Sanah 216 hours, Galuh 216 hours, Rahmah 96 hours, Santi 96 hours, Lisnawati 120 hours, Nurmiah 96 hours, Hikmah 216 hours, Sumiah 216 hours, and Amamiah 216 hours. According to Isni, et al (2022), the division of working time has a positive influence on work balance. This shows that work-life balance also has a positive relationship with job satisfaction. Based on the results of this research, the division of working time has no relationship with job satisfaction, but can add work-life balance as a mediation between the division of working time and job satisfaction.

Productivity Income

Data on the productivity income of Purun mat woven craftsmen every day and every month, as in the following table.

Table 3. Productivity Income

No	Date	Name	Type	1 Day	1 Sunday	1 Month	Price	1 Month Income/Rp
1	22/05/2022	Rina	Mat	2	12	48	25.000	1.200.000
2	22/05/2022	Sanah	Mat	2	12	48	25.000	1.200.000
3	22/05/2022	Galuh	Mat	2	12	48	25.000	1.200.000
4	22/05/2022	Rahmah	Mat	1	6	24	25.000	6.00.000
5	22/05/2022	Santi	Mat	1	6	24	25.000	6.00.000
6	22/05/2022	Lisnawati	Mat	1	6	24	25.000	6.00.000
7	22/05/2022	Nurmiah	Mat	1	6	24	25.000	6.00.000
8	22/05/2022	Hikmah	Mat	2	12	48	25.000	1.200.000
9	22/05/2022	Sumiah	Mat	2	12	48	25.000	1.200.000
10	22/05/2022	Amamiah	Mat	2	12	48	25.000	1.200.000

Source: Research Data (2022)

Variable Costs

The results of research on 10 respondents vary in the variable costs that must be incurred by purun woven craftsmen, there are two variations in one month in the calculation, namely the variable costs incurred to buy purun and the dye costs by respondents, the variations in respondents' costs can be seen in the table below.

Table 4. Variable Costs of Variations One and Two

No	Component	TFC/ Variation one	Amount/month (Rp)	TFC/ Variation two	Amount/month (Rp)
1	Purun	12 ikat	300.000	6 ikat	150.000
2	Dye/red	1 ons	50.000	½ ons	25.000
3	Dye/green	1 ons	50.000	½ ons	25.000
	Total		400.000		200.000

Source: Research Data (2022)

The results of research conducted through interview respondents show that there are costs that must be incurred within one month of production activities to purchase raw materials for purun, such as purchasing dyes or kasumba at a price of one bundle of Rp. 25,000,- In the variation of one respondent with the costs incurred to buy 12 bundles of purun at a price of Rp. 300,000,- and 1 ounce of red dye and 1 ounce of green dye with a price of IDR 50,000 for one color, so the total costs incurred by variation one are IDR. 400,000,- in one month and the costs incurred by variation two by purchasing 6 bundles of purun at a price of IDR 25,000,- per bundle. The total costs incurred by respondents by purchasing 6 bundles of purun for Rp. 150,000,- buy ½ ounce red dye for Rp. 25,000,- and ½ ounce green dye costs Rp. 25,000,- total variable costs incurred vary by two Rp. 200,000,- in one month of production. Fahriani (2020), variable costs are costs that change directly and proportionally to changes in the level of activity or volume of production produced, in contrast to fixed costs which remain constant regardless of production levels, variable costs increase when production increases and decrease when production decreases. Understanding and managing variable costs from this research is very important because it has a direct impact on profitability. By calculating the variable costs per unit of product, you can determine the appropriate selling price to achieve the profit target obtained..

Total Production Costs

Total production costs are a number of costs incurred in one month. These costs consist of variable fixed costs. Fixed costs are costs incurred for production facilities and can be used many times. For more details regarding the total production costs incurred by purun mat woven craftsmen, see the table below. Based on the average total production cost for one month of variation one respondent is IDR. 400,000,-

and variation two of Rp. 200,000,- there are differences in the total production costs of the 10 respondents, this depends on how much purun or raw materials are used.

Table 5. Total Production Costs for Purun Craftsmen Vary by One Month

Cost type	Total cost of variation one (Rp/month)	Variation two (Rp/month)
Variable	400.000	200.000
Total	400.000	200.000

Source: Research Data (2022)

The selling price of woven purun mat crafts is determined by the craftsman based on the costs incurred while managing the woven crafts. Based on the research results, various data were obtained for the number of productivity of purun mat woven craftsmen in one month, varying from one to 48 pieces of mat with a selling price of Rp. 25,000 per mat and productivity variations of two 24 mats at a price of IDR 25,000 per mat.

Table 6. Total Productivity of Purun Woven Craftsmen in One Month

Variation	Productivity/month	Price (Rp)	Sales/month (Rp)	Income (Rp)
1	48/ sheet	25.000	1.200.000	800.000
2	24/ sheet	25.000	600.000	400.000

Source: Research Data (2022)

The amount of income or profit obtained by purun mat weaving craftsmen is obtained from the income minus the production costs of the craft activity. mathematically written in a formula (Soekartawi, 2003). Based on total income for variations of one Rp. 800,000,- and income for variation two is IDR. 400,000,- Purun woven craftsmen also have other income from cutting rubber and there are also those who do not have additional income.

Other Income

In general, a job definitely has certain obstacles in determining its production results, for example if there is another business such as carving rubber, this can usually be influenced by the number of rubber tree trunks that produce to be cut and natural factors also greatly influence when carving rubber, for example rainy and dry weather. prolonged. If the weather is rainy when the rubber sap is still dripping, it will be washed away by rainwater, and dry weather is also not good for cutting rubber because during the dry season the water supply for rubber is reduced, this has a big impact on the less rubber sap that will be produced. The following are respondents who have additional income in the same family and those who do not have other income.

Table 7. Additional Income

NO	Name	Sales/week (Kg)	Purun Price (Kg)	One month (Rp)	Other income (Rp)
1	Rina	54	800.000	1.728.000	2.528.000
2	Sanah	45	800.000	1.440.000	2.240.000
3	Galuh	36	800.000	1.152.000	2.752.000
4	Rahmah	60	400.000	1.920.000	2.320.000
5	Santi	48	400.000	1.536.000	1.936.000
6	Lisnawati	-	-	-	400.000
7	Nurmiah	60	400.000	1.920.000	2.320.000
8	Hikmah	-	800.000	-	800.000
9	Sumiah	50	800.000	1.600.000	2.400.000
10	Amamiah	66	800.000	2.112.000	2.912.000

Source: Research Data (2022)

We compare the total monthly income of purun woven craftsmen with the Kuala Kapuas Regency UMK in 2022, which is Rp. 2,909,962,- as stated in Governor's Decree No. 188.44/604/2020 Concerning Regency/City Minimum Wages in 2021. The income of purun woven craftsmen is that 1 respondent meets the UMK and 9 respondents do not meet the Regency Minimum Wage (UMK). And the welfare level of purun woven craftsmen at the research site is still not good enough to survive on a daily basis. Purun in this district is done by 100% of women and generally purun is used as a side job (Fatriani, 2010).

Conclusion

The total income of the purun woven craftsmen for each respondent varies and still does not meet the Regency or City Minimum Wage standards, so that to cover living needs comes from other income such as carving rubber, and the level of welfare is still not good, just to be able to survive on a daily basis.

It is hoped that the researchers' suggestions will be able to create tools for flattening purun, the place for the coloring process should be given a roof, utilize working time more efficiently, be more focused so that productivity can increase and the results obtained will be greater, always trying to create new motifs. Purun woven craftsmen can also work together to request guidance and training in developing the purun woven craft business from village agencies.

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